

An updated review of the polymorphic crab spider *Thomisus citrinellus* Simon, 1875

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ABSTRACT: *Thomisus spinifer* O. Pickard-Cambridge (1872) was described from specimens from Jordan. However, the name *T. spinifer* was preoccupied, rendering it invalid. *Thomisus citrinellus*, described by Simon (1875) based on a female specimen from the southern side of the Pyrenees, between France and Spain, became the accepted name to replace *T. spinifer*. But the nomenclatural history of the species is complex, involving multiple synonyms. In the description of *T. citrinellus*, an irregular triangular marking and short transverse bands on the abdomen are distinctive for the species, and the legs have bands and spots. These markings correspond with observations of the species by different authors throughout Africa. With more than 100 photographs available of live spiders, at least two colour morphs in shades of pink or brown are seen.

Keywords: biodiversity, colour change, geographic distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida

INTRODUCTION

Thomisus spinifer O. Pickard-Cambridge (1872) was described from a specimen collected from Jordan. However, the name *T. spinifer* was already preoccupied, rendering it invalid according to the International Code of Zoological Nomenclature (ICZN). The species *Thomisus citrinellus*, described by Simon (1875), has become the accepted name to replace *T. spinifer* (Roewer, 1955) and is listed as such in the World Spider Catalog (2026), with verified taxonomic standing in the Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS). However, its nomenclatural history is complex, involving multiple synonyms. *Thomisus citrinellus* was described from a female sampled from “Pyrénées espagnoles” an area on the southern side of the Pyrenees mountain range between France and Spain. The World Spider Catalog (2026) listed *T. citrinellus* as widely distributed across Spain, France, Cyprus, Turkey, Africa, Seychelles, Yemen (incl. Socotra), Israel, and Iraq and possibly Iran. In this paper the presence of *T. citrinellus* in Africa is reviewed with notes on the different colour morphs found.

METHODS

As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), many *T. citrinellus* specimens from several localities in South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015) were sampled, and voucher specimens are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida at the Agricultural Research Council, Pretoria (NCA). As part of the SANSA Virtual Museum photograph database (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012) numerous images were received that provided additional information on the species. Images of the species was also sourced from iNaturalist, a global community science platform.

RESULTS

***Thomisus spinifer* records from Africa:** Publications indicate that *T. citrinellus* has a wide distribution throughout Africa. In South Africa, Dippenaar-Schoeman (1983) revised the *Thomisus* species of southern Africa, and examined numerous specimens from Africa housed in several museums abroad. *Thomisus citrinellus* are presently reported from: Algeria (Beladjal *et al.*, 2025); Botswana (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Kassimatis, 2002); Chad (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1983); Egypt (Sallam, 2012); Djibouti (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1989); Ethiopia (Caporiacco, 1941; Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1983); French Guinea (Millot, 1942); Kenya (Caporiacco, 1949; Kioko *et al.*, 2021); Mali (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1983); Mozambique (Lessert, 1936); Namibia (NCA); Senegal (Simon, 1886; Caporiacco, 1941); South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2023); Tanzania (Russell-Smith, 2020); Uganda (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1983) and Zimbabwe (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1983).

Figures 1–2. *Thomisus citrinellus*. 1. Female from Heidelberg in Gauteng. 2. Male from Hoedspruit. Credits: 1. Johan van Zyl. 2. Peter Webb.

Figure 3–7. *Thomisus citrinellus*. 3. Female habitus from French Guinea. 4. Epigyne. 5. Female habitus from South Africa. 6. Epigyne. 7. *Thomisus citrinellus* female, first record from eSwatini. Credits: 3–4. After Millot (1942). 5–6. After Dippenaar-Schoeman (1983). 7. Phil White.

Female diagnostic characters: Simon (1875) described the holotype female, noting abdominal markings consisting of an irregular triangular dark mark followed by short transverse bands, and mentions the bands and spots on the legs. This corresponds to the markings shown in Fig. 1. Only in 1886 did Simon mention the darker mediolateral bands on the carapace of a female from Senegal. In the same paper, he provided the first drawing of the male palp (Fig. 15). Both Lessert (1936), with specimens from Mozambique, and Caporiacco (1941), with specimens from Senegal and Ethiopia, observed the dark mediolateral bands on the carapace, the bands on the anterior legs, and the markings on the abdomen. Millot (1942) provided the first illustrations of a female from French Guinea (Figs 4 & 5). He clearly illustrated the abdominal markings as described by Simon (1875). But due to the complex nomenclatural history, the invalidity of *T. spinifer*, the subspecies *T. spinifer decorata* (Millot, 1942); *T. spinifer simoni*, *T. spinifer obscurus* and *T. spinifer maculata* Caporiacco (1941; 1949) were regarded as synonyms of *T. citrinellus* by Dippenaar-Schoeman (1983).

Colour morphs: In museum specimens or alcohol-collected individuals, pink pigments may degrade post-mortem, appearing fawn to brown (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2025b). This is especially relevant when comparing live vs preserved colouration. With more than 100 images of live *T. citrinellus* available, two colour morphs have been recognised.

A few specimens are fawn with brown markings (Figs 15–17), while the majority are white with pink markings (Figs 1, 8–14). The pink colouration in *T. citrinellus* is primarily due to stable, lipochrome pigments in the hypodermis, rather than reversible pigment dynamics like those seen in yellow-white transitions of other *Thomisus* species (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2025a). The pink colour is more persistent and not withdrawn or redistributed like ommochromes (yellow pigments). The cuticle and hypodermis are partially transparent, allowing pink pigments to interact with underlying guanine crystals. These markings are not known to change with background, supporting their role as fixed traits (Gawryszewski *et al.*, 2015; Herberstein & Gawryszewski, 2012). Lipochromes that accumulate in hypodermal cells form the characteristic markings as described by Simon (1875; 1886). This pink colouration tends to intensify with age (Fig. 14), suggesting a developmental trajectory rather than an environmentally induced change. Brown colouration sometimes replaces pink in *T. citrinellus*. It could be melanin accumulation that overrides lighter pigments, turning pink to brown or ommochrome degradation that may also result in brownish tones replacing pink.

If pink is derived from unstable pigments (e.g. ommochromes or carotenoids), it may fade or oxidise into brown under certain conditions. Brown may be favoured in habitats with leaf litter, grasses, and bark, which offer better camouflage (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2025a).

Figure 8–14. Examples of pink morphs showing the different variations of the basic markings. Credits: 8. Peter Webb. 9. Sally Adam. 10. Lynette Rudmann. 11. Les Oates. 12. Cecile Roux. 13. Andrea Sander. 14. S. Boyd.

Figure 15–17. Examples of brown morphs showing the different variations of the basic markings. Credits: 15. Linda Wiese. 16. Vida van der Walt. 17. Andrea Sander.

Figure 15–18. *Thomisus citrinellus* male. 15. Male palp drawing after Simon (1886) from Senegal. 16. Male habitus after Millot (1942). 17. Male palp after Dippenaar-Schoeman (1989). 18. Male (Ian Anderson).

Male: The male is much smaller than the female. Simon (1886) provided the first drawing of the male palp (Fig. 15), which corresponds to that of Dippenaar-Schoeman (1983; 1989) (Fig. 17). The palp is very distinctive as it bears two slightly curved retrolateral apophyses on the palpal tibia and a large downward-inclined tegulum. In the male (Figs 1, 16 & 18), the carapace is brown and covered with long erect setae. Legs with front legs brown, tibiae I and II darker brown with metatarsi with a faint darker band that varies between specimens; posterior legs pale brown. The abdomen is covered with numerous erect setae. However, the bodies of males of several species resemble each other; sometimes, only bands on the front legs vary. But the leg bands also vary between specimens, and the only way to identify the species is to examine the male palp. Also, assuming that males found on females' abdomens are the same species as the females is not always correct, as they are frequently killed by females.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Thomisus citrinellus is a common species and is currently known from 19 African countries. The female is recognised by the mediolateral bands on the carapace and, on the abdomen, an irregular triangular marking followed by short, wavy posterior bands. The abdomen sometimes has a round, dark spot on each tubercle. In the male several species resemble each other; sometimes, only differing by the bands on the front legs. But the leg bands also vary between specimens, and the only way to identify the species correctly is to examine the male palp. Also, males found on females' abdomens are not always of the same species, and they are then killed (Fig. 21).

With the large number of images available, two colour morphs, pink or brown, have been identified. However most specimens are pink, and the darker body markings are present in all, but do vary in shape (Figs 7-14). *Thomisus citrinellus* seems not to change colour as observed in some other *Thomisus* species.

This was also observed by Levy (1973), who reported that the species is unable to change colour. However, we observed some variations in body patterns. In Fig. 19, the colouration is dark and possibly melanin based. Melanistic morphs in Thomisidae are possibly underreported due to seasonal, sexual, or ontogenetic variation (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2025a) but have been observed in several thomisid genera. In Fig. 20, the female has all the pink markings but with a yellow undertone.

With further research and more information now available, *Thomisus ghesquierei* Lessert, 1943, as reported on by Dippenaar-Schoeman (2023), might in reality be the brown morph of *T. citrinellus*. However, specimens are needed to study genitalia for confirmation.

Figure 19. *Thomisus citrinellus* female dark variation (Heather and Andrew Hodgson)

Figure 20. *Thomisus citrinellus* female with yellow tint (Vida vd Walt)

Figure 21. *Thomisus citrinellus* female feeding on a male that is not conspecific.

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